
**COMMUNICATION SKILLS FOR ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE AND CAREER
DEVELOPMENT: ENGLISH AS THE GLOBAL LANGUAGE OF
COMMUNICATION**

R.Sujatha Rani

MA, MPhil

Ph.D Scholar

Sri Padmavathi Mahila Viswa Vidyalayam

Tirupathi

Abstract:

The linguistic properties facilitate of expression based upon the cultural and politico-social reasons English have become the Global Language of Communication. The cultural and political domination of the British over the large parts of the globe made this possible and inevitable too. The literary treasure of English and the flexibility of the language in co-existing with the several other western languages also have helped it a lot in becoming the Global Language. The most important reason for English to develop into a universal language is its colonial spread in many parts of the globe on both sides plus the cultural and civilized attraction and influence the British could spread wherever they established their colonies. This political advantage of the British has mainly instrumental in making English a universal language. Unless they too develop their communication skills in English, they realized that they would become backward in every respect particularly as far as their socio-political and civilization advancements are concerned. So, to avoid such a situation every sensible nation made it a point that the communication skills in English are but to be made a part of their academic and intellectual progress. Because of this particular realization, the communication skills in the English language have become a hallmark of modern intellectual excellence and professional proficiency. In summary, the English language with all its historic significance, modern-day importance in several ways of social, economic, linguistic, political and even cultural spheres of modern human life has proved its worth as a language of global communication which unless is recognized, followed and practiced by all the other linguistic groups and nations they would lag behind in all-round development and paced advancement in every field of human activity. Particularly it would be a loss for them in the case of their intellectual, academic and professional advancement without which they cannot firmly get a hold as individual nations in the comity of advanced nations. Communication in the modern world has become the key for global contact. English has attained a pivotal role in global communication. Without English as the language of global communication, the world would once again go back to the days of fragmented pieces of unconnected nations, in the medieval period.

Keywords: global language, communication, civilized

English has become the Global Language of Communication:

Communication is essentially a device for any living being to convey one's thought or idea or even an opinion to the other. Without communication, living beings would have had to live an isolated life even if living among crowds. We find every species of life on earth has its own way and style of communication with its fellow creatures. This communication chiefly can be divided into two separate varieties, verbal and non-verbal. We find all the non-human living beings, as they have not been bestowed with speech communication among themselves in various non-verbal ways, whereas the only man who has been exclusively endowed with the greatest boon of speech communicates verbally. David Crystal explained the mixer of the culture and tradition about communication in English in his book English as a Global Language second edition, he comments...

New methods of mass production demanded a new way of mass hauling. In particular, as far as the language was concerned, the distribution of daily newspapers on a bulky level would not have been likely without a railway system and, later, a road network capable of transmitting and escalating weighty vehicles.

Again in the spoken assortment of communication, language has become the most effective, powerful device of communication that helps not only just to communicate with the fellow human beings but also to strengthen and develop bonds of cordiality, sentiment, intellectual and other varieties of human evolution. In the process of the development of communication the language, as has become the most effective and powerful device, naturally the skills have become more important to be developed to facilitate the communication, in a still more effective and still easier and still clearer way of communication. Of all the innumerable languages on both side of the globe the most wide-spread, widely influenced and highly elastic and versatility-rich language of English has become the world language of communication in the modern day world. But to gain this top position of communication all over the world, indeed English has had its own greater properties of linguistic expansion as its cultural and civilized niceties and attractions which helped the language easily accepted by other non-English linguistic groups. To cite a ready and most common example – “yes”, “no” like words are so simple yet great with their expression that helps one communicate in a variety of ways with hundreds of meanings conveyed with a little difference in their pronunciation along with the expression of our feeling. How a language plays a vital role in globalization is explained in World Wide Web...

“Looking at the situation at present, the best action that a country must take is to confiscate first the obstructions towards globalization like the linguistic and communication barriers. Language and communication play a fundamental task in globalization specifically in unifying the world's culture and economy through the utilization of information technology and medium.”

In fact today there are a number of English languages all over the world with several dialectical differences depending upon the local situations, cultures, and patterns of habit etc., Hitherto only two main varieties of English. British English and American English are popularly known to the world. But as the time progressed and the patronage of English as a language, as also a culture has caught up with several European, African and even Asian nations depending upon the native varieties of culture, English has also proliferated into heterogeneous varieties, though the fundamental set up and peculiarities of English are not lost. There have been various developments, modifications and facial changes in the language. It is all because of the various differences among the local, cultural moorings and civilization and linguistic influences that English which once was a monolithic language has proliferated into various regional varieties, of course not losing its basic commonness and fundamental structural uniformity. David Crystal enlightened his observations about the development of communication in global level in his book English as a World Language, he says ...

More such languages endure today in countries which formerly belonged to the European colonial nations,, a language is admitted from outside the society, such as English or French, because of the political, economic, or religious persuade a foreign power.

The most advantageous and effective quality and characteristic of the language of English that helped and still helping it to penetrate into various corners of the globe is it's a facility of expression and flexibility of accommodation added to the spirit of that language of *"live and let live."*

The specialty of English in becoming the Global Language:

As for the specialty and exclusive quality of English to become the global language the first and foremost property of it is to be given its true place i.e. the unique quality of flexibility and felicitation of expression actually these two great traits have first been primarily responsible for English to turn into literarily the affluent, culturally the strongest of all the languages of both the East and the West. The hoary past literature in that language has been possible to be grown into a great treasure that has been fondly preserved not only by the native literary folks of the language but all over the globe where the taste for the literary values and excellence have been cherished even for today and most likely forever. Dr.Raghukul Tilak explained his views about Indo English literature in his book The Serpent and The Rope fifth edition, he clarifies...

It should also be noted that "Indo-English literature" reverses the basic principle that the language of translation should be the translator's own first language. Indo-English literature consists of translations from the 'mother tongue' into English which is rarely the first language of an Indian. Hence in making such translations, the translator must see to it that his language is not

only grammatically accurate but also has idiomatic accuracy of a high degree.

This particular richness of literature and the flexibility and facility of expression along with its grammatical and other linguistic special features several non-English groups of people all over the world got attracted towards that language. Once they are drawn to it they got so thoroughly attached to the language because of the influence of the literary splendor and linguistic glamour of that language that has even overtaken and overpowered by the influences and attachments of the various non-English groups with their native languages or even their own mother tongues.

Of course, there has been the major influence of the English race as a ruling one with its colonial expansion on the political planes as also the cultural and linguistic influence of the English as a race over several of the non-English groups of people all over the world. The most important and the significant factors that have helped English easily spread its influence and directly get penetrated into the depths of the local civilized groups of people is its colonial dominance. But unless the language of English has such a great and unique property of acceptability and power of accommodation and adjustment, as also the capacity to absorb simply colonial domination could not have been possible to help it become a readily and thoroughly accepted global language. Prof. Jacob Tharu, in his article English Proficiency in the Context of Globalization: A picture of Diversity, he explains...

In any discussion of English today, one point that is taken for granted and emphasized is that it is a world language.....However, there is a second and more important aspect of this widespread use of the language.

Reasons that helped English become the universal language: While the literary richness of English as a language and the cultural and civilized charisma of it have been mainly responsible for making English a universally appealing language, several incidental factors too helped it and supported it to get firmly established and entrenched as the universal language. In this context, it should be noted that even though the UNO has recognized several other languages like French too as official languages, it is only English in which language most of the work is done even by the UNO itself as also by the member nations. That fact accounts for the domineering linguistic features of English that made it readily usable and easily acceptable and even voluntarily patronized as the universal language. Dr. Pramod K Nayar brings together information about how English helps in imperial commerce and government, in his material The Arrival of English in India, he holds...

The English-educated intelligentsia, mainly in Calcutta, was increasingly drawn into imperial commerce and government. New urban elite was thus born – and this was made possible because their command over English gave them access to the seat of power. This elite in Bengal came to be known as the

‘bhadralok’ (respectable people). The *bhadralok* did not possess great economic power.

To be more frank and pointed, the effect of English as the universally accepted and practiced language of communication can be traced to the fact that a kind of superiority complex has been developed among the users of English as a language everywhere in such a way that the groups of people who cannot speak in English are considered inferior by their intellectual and cultural levels. The way the language of English has got to the topmost position the universal language is indeed an inspiring one to several of the other local languages of the civilized nations to attain acceptability even at their respective national levels. The knowledge of English literature and the skills of communication in that language have attained such a great charismatic place among the various literary and linguistic groups of the nations that the English knowing ones have been readily considered to be all-knowing by the others. All such factors have together now made the language of English firmly positioned itself as the universal language.

The essentiality of English as a Global Language of Communication: In summary, the English language with all its historic significance, modern-day importance in several ways of social, economic, linguistic, political and even cultural spheres of modern human activity has proved its worth as a language of global communication which unless is recognized, followed and practiced by all the other linguistic groups and nations they would lag behind in all-round development and paced advancement in every field of human activity. Particularly it would be a loss for them in the case of their intellectual, academic and professional advancement without which they cannot firmly get a hold as individual nations in the comity of advanced nations. Dr.B Parvathi, composed information, about the English language won recognition in India along with regional languages, in her article Indian Languages and Literature, she holds...

With Independence, the question of a common language for the nation naturally came up. There was no consensus in the matter in the Constituent Assembly on this question.....Thus in addition to Hindi and English, eighteen regional languages of India have won statutory recognition which is a unique situation in linguistic terms for any country.

Communication in the modern world has become the key for global contact. English has attained a pivotal role in global communication. Without English as the language of global communication, the world would once again go back to the days of fragmented pieces of unconnected nations, in the medieval period. Actually speaking communication has been the root cause and chief factor that has made the *Global Village* concept a reality.

Conclusion:

Today the entire world of communication is solely dependent upon only one language that is English. It is impossible for any civilized group or nation all over the world to communicate with any other nation or group without the use of English. Minus English today it is a big, un-fill able vacuum and void in the whole world of communication. It is quite unimaginable that without the language of English as the vehicle of communication there can ever be any sensible and clear way of communication anywhere all over the world. It would only be reversing the clock and driving the human groups back to the days of medieval periods. Without English being the global language of communication. It has become so intensely interwoven into the fabric of the living culture that even among the members of the same group belonging to any other language as their mother tongue, they too essentially do the communication so automatically and so naturally in the global language of English setting aside their own mother tongue. Unless there is a conscious and well-intended effort by the groups of non-English languages to communicate among themselves in their own native languages or mother tongues they are not that easily able to communicate with the same ease and the facility of expression as they do in English is the ready and direct proof of the essentiality of English as a global language of communication. Without English as the global language of communication, the entire world of communication would become darker and splintered into various fragments of communication-less groups groping in that darkness for a common alternative device of communication, which is practically impossible and even unimaginable in the present day situation. Not just as a language but as a device of great communication with all its varied skills and properties English today rules over the entire world of communication.

References:

- Crystal David, English as a Global Language, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Canto Classic edition, 2012.
- Crystal David, English as a Global Language, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Canto Classic edition, 2012, pp.82
- <http://www.theborneopost.com/?p=38904>
- Crystal David, English as a Global Language, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, Canto Classic edition, 2012, pp.11
- Tilak Raghukul, The Serpent and The Rope, Rama Brothers Educational Publishers, Karol Bagh, New Delhi, pp.2-3
- Prof.Jacob Tharu, English in Use: The Abilities of Individuals, Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Open University, Hyderabad, 2011, pp.44
- Dr.Pramod K Nayar, Indian English Literature, Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Open University, Hyderabad, 2010, pp.5

- Dr.B Parvathi, Aspects of Language and Their Relation to Literature, Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Open University, Hyderabad, 2011, pp.154
- Naik, M.K. A History of Indian English Literature. New Delhi: Sahitya Academi, 1982.
- Mukherjee Alok, This Gift of English, Orient Blackswan, 2009.